

Multi-State Reliability Requirements for Complex Systems

Jason L. Cook, ASQ CRE

Key Words: Multi-state, Allocation, Modeling

SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

Few complex systems exhibit a binary set of states, that is only simple systems are limited to the basic states of operational and failed. Complex systems and Systems of Systems (SoS) take on multiple degraded states between the fully operational and fully failed extremes. However, reliability requirements often lack the necessary information to adequately allocate multi-state reliability to the sub-systems and components. Specifically, the criticality of functional failures is not defined in the requirements phase but rather, it is done just prior to test. A proposed requirements generation and allocation method is presented to enable more robust requirement sets specific to multi-state systems and SoS which in turn enables more effective and efficient Design for Reliability practices.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Army acquisition process now mandates that reliability be included as a Key Performance Parameter (KPP) for all systems. This fact underscores the importance of this technical performance measure that is applied, in some fashion, to all systems and products. The popular metrics for these systems, with the exception of single shot devices such as ammunition, are usually multi-state. Specifically, the Army uses the terms System Abort (SA), Essential Function Failure (EFF), and Non-Essential Function Failure (NEFF) as reliability failure classifications. A system abort is the most severe type of failure and it results in a system being “down” or in a non-operational, non-mission capable state. Thus, operational availability (Ao) is a function of the frequency of failures in this class. Mean Time Between System Abort (MTBSA) is most often the metric used to measure that frequency.

The gap in this process is for most programs is that the sub-set of functions whose failure results in a SA is not defined until the system is well into design or in the worst cases not until testing begins. This limits the designers’ ability to allocate such a metric and efficiently focus reliability design resources to the hardware items that support that most critical sub-set of functions. It also precludes intelligent architecture designs intended to provide a fault tolerant system or SoS through either functional or physical redundancies for functions of such criticality.

The current process is as follows. The Army uses a

document called the Failure Definition and Scoring Criteria (FDSC) to define and classify failures into the above categories. Previously, the war-fighting customer will have defined his reliability requirements within a Capabilities Description Document (CDD) – previously termed an Operational Requirements Document (ORD). The CDD or ORD is available before design activities commence, however the inclusion of an MTBSA requirement within such a document without the qualifying and clarifying FDSC provides an ill-defined requirement.

This, among other causes, has contributed to the less than optimal track record on reliability requirement achievement for complex Army systems. For this reason, it is proposed that all functional requirements should be written with an associated failure severity or failure class in order that the reliability metrics of such multi-state systems are defined at the time of the requirements generation. Such a practice will enable the designers’ to understand the multi-state reliability requirement as well as optimally and accurately allocate that requirement. The designer will then be able to make the most efficient and effective use of the always limited reliability dedicated resources (e.g. test and analysis budget). Similarly, when the cost and weight of redundancy is the only solution this can be applied to the most critical components. Finally, and perhaps most significantly contracts including such requirements will no longer be subjective but rather definitive.

This same structure may then be used for reliability requirements for a SoS - which is surely multi-state. The SoS in the DoD vernacular generally refers to a number of heterogeneous systems which have individual inherent capabilities as well as capabilities that are combinatorial due to their SoS relations. More plainly, a system has mobility and lethality capability but the SoS provides networking and data fusion capability that no single platform retains when isolated.

2 RELATED WORK

The reliability allocation problem is a classic topic of research in the literature. The notion of multi-state reliability of systems and components provides further complexities and the associated areas of research. The Reliability Allocation Problem (RAP) can take several forms but the ultimate goal is system architecture and component reliability requirement set that meet the system’s top level reliability. Ramirez-Marquez and Coit [1] proposed a heuristic approach for when the

redundancy allocation problem is formulated with the objective of minimizing cost, when the system exhibits a multi-state reliability, with system-level performance constraints. Ramirez-Marquez and Coit [2] introduce the use of Monte Carlo simulation to evaluate a multi-state network, developing an efficient and accurate approach to approximate the Multi-state Two-terminal Reliability (M2TR). Li and Pham [4] present a generalized multi-state degraded system reliability model subject to multiple competing failure processes, including two degradation processes, and random shocks. The condition of the multi-state systems is classified by a finite number of states to provide a determination of system reliability.

Rocco and Muselli [5] presented a machine-learning-based methodology, extended to based on the procedure of Hamming Clustering, which is capable to deal with multi-state systems. Kapur and Satitsatian [6] also addressed the M2TR analysis problem, proposing that lower boundary points can be used to obtain an exact reliability value and confidence bounds. Yi et al [7] present a method by which they take complex generating system (CGS) represented by their multi-state reliability equivalents and then use the universal generating functions (UGFs) of these equivalents to evaluate the reliability of a particular GS. A genetic algorithm (GA) is then used to solve the optimization problem.

Ramirez-Marquez et al [3,8] also proposed methods to determine reliability criticality for multi-state systems, specifically they present criticality indexes with the M2TR impact as the measure of criticality. Zuo et al [9] published an efficient recursive algorithm for the reliability evaluation of Multi-state terminal pair networks based on the Sum of Disjoint Products (SDP) principle; naming their convention as the Recursive Sum of Disjoint Products (RSDP) algorithm. Agarwal and Gupta [12] present a heuristic for a series-parallel system where the components are binary and are characterized by capacity, reliability and cost. The heuristic claims improved efficiency of solution quality and computational time, as compared to existing genetic algorithms.

Kuo and Wan [13] provide a comprehensive summary of optimization applicable to the multi-state problem; reviewing the universal generating-function-based method, multi-objective optimization, ant colony optimization and hybrid optimization.

3 TECHNICAL CONSIDERATIONS

In this paper, we don't set out to redefine or improve the mathematics of multi-state evaluation or allocation but rather the process by which a multi-state system requirements and subsequently the system it self is developed. Specifically, we address the systems engineering framework that must be in place to adequately define the states of a system for multi-state reliability allocation and design.

Put simply, if a requirement is predicated upon the time between, time until or probability of a specific event or events occurring, those events must be defined a-priori for that

requirement to have meaning. If the user is concerned with the frequency of system aborts, then he must enumerate the functions whose loss results in such a condition to truly express the intent and meaning of that requirement. Accordingly, rigorous systems engineering principles require that this definition be allocated along with the requirement to lower levels. That is, traceability will not only include allocation of reliability to sub-systems and components but also allocation of functional severity.

This paper defines a structure, notation, and process that can be employed manually or within the requirements management tools such as DOORS. The proposal is neither mathematically complex nor complicated to employ but to date it remains only a proposal. Despite the simplicity, the rewards are many.

To this end, first a set of notation is established to communicate the proposed methodology and process. The notation shall then be used throughout the paper. However, before proceeding we first set down a base assumption that all components have exponentially distributed failure rates that are characterized by the popular metric of Mean time Between Failure (MTBF) or its inverse, Failure Rate (λ). Let us further clarify that this is a simplifying assumption and not one that is true in many (or any) systems. This method can and should be easily adapted to include other failure distributions but as our goal is a requirements framework and mostly a cultural paradigm shift (not a mathematical contribution) the simpler assumption is adopted herein. Along a similar line of thinking, we shall assume that individual components within the system have binary failure modes such that they are either failed or operating and only the system and subsystems exhibit multi-state performance based upon the functions that are available.

First, we define the highest level of requirements (typically from the customer) as the originating requirements, such as from an ORD or CDD, as the set Φ . We assume that these requirements have previously been reduced to *first principle* type requirements. That is, they are not tiered and decomposed but rather stand alone requirements. That is not to say that they in no way interact but simply that these are explicit and not derived from other requirements. It is also critical that functional requirements are truly functional and the often seen folly of including detail requirements within this set is avoided.

Next, if there are k requirements in this set of originating requirements and they are indexed by j taking the values $j = 1, 2, \dots, k$ so Φ_j is the j^{th} requirement. This set of functional requirements represents the full capability of a given system. When $\Phi_j = 1$ then the system is in a state such that the j^{th} function is performed or performable as required. When it is completely absent we say that $\Phi_j = 0$.

Further, we define the system (or SoS) state as a function of these functional states. This state is denoted as Ω , where

$$\Omega = f(\Phi) \quad (1)$$

$\dot{\Phi}$ is a subset of Φ representing the minimum cut-set of functions required in order to meet the functional requirements of the system to be considered in an operational state. We define a system that is fully operational by $\Omega = 1$. A system that is operational but degraded in some fashion is given by $\Omega = 0.5$. That is,

$$\Omega = 1 \text{ if } \forall j = 1, 2, \dots, k \ \Phi_j = 1 \quad (2)$$

$$\Omega = 0.5 \text{ if for any } j \ \Phi_j = 0 \text{ but } \forall j \subset \dot{\Phi}; \Phi_j = 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\Omega = 0 \text{ if for any } j \subset \dot{\Phi}; \Phi_j = 0 \quad (4)$$

With this additional qualification of the functional requirements, we can now represent the system functional failure severity via traditional reliability methods of Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) or Reliability Block Diagrams (RBD).

Next, X shall represent the system's components and i indexes this set of a total number n components; individually denoted as $X_i \forall i=1, 2, \dots, n$.

To complete the system structure we define a graph $\mathbf{G}(\Phi, \mathbf{X})$ which maps functions (Φ) to components (\mathbf{X}). This graph is an adjacency matrix which, by definition, includes elements of \mathbf{G} as g_{ij} which represent a link between Φ_j and X_i and \mathbf{G} is of size $k \times n$. That is, $g_{ij} = 1$ if component X_i is required in support of function Φ_j .

With this notation in place, it is asserted that to define functional failure severity in the requirements generation and decomposition process of systems engineering each functional requirement should be classified accordingly. That is, the membership of each Φ_j in $\dot{\Phi}$ or the absence of that membership should be known at the time when the reliability requirement is developed. Mathematically, if the failure rate is assumed exponential then we know that the following is true

$$R(t) = \exp(-\lambda t) \quad (5)$$

Further, we can state that;

$$P(\Phi_j = 1 \forall j \subset \dot{\Phi}) = \exp(-t/MTBSA) \quad (6)$$

Next, it is further asserted that minimal new work is required to define the components whose failure constitutes a system abort (SA). This knowledge comes naturally after functional to physical allocation. That is, once each requirement is tied (traced) to a specific component or set of components the functional severity can likewise be traced.

Then, when this proper requirements traceability is done and the graph \mathbf{G} is defined the subset of components supporting the critical functions $\dot{\Phi}$ can be obtained, we shall refer to this subset of \mathbf{X} as $\dot{\mathbf{X}}$.

Since we have previously adopted the exponential distribution and the binary failure assumptions we can qualify the reliability of each component by $MTBF_i$, representing the reliability of component X_i . Conversely the failure rate of the same component is given by λ_i .

Resulting in

$$\frac{1}{MTBSA} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{MTBF_i} \forall i \subset \dot{X}_i \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{1}{MTBSA} = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \forall i \subset \dot{X}_i \quad (8)$$

In a requirements management tool such as DOORS, implementation requires only a requirement attribute for this classification and populating that field with the appropriate functional severity. Subsequently, the functional to physical mapping of requirements to components is a standard systems engineering practice supported by most software applications. It is done in almost every program and is certainly not a new concept. However, appending the functional failure severity to this process before hand provides a large value to the reliability and systems engineer concerned with technically defining and then achieving a multi-state reliability requirement such as MTBSA. The classification and traceability, documented in $\dot{\Phi}$ and $\mathbf{G}(\Phi, \mathbf{X})$, is then a natural artifact of this *way of doing business*. The individual functional severities shall be denoted as $\dot{\Phi}_j$ such that if loss of function Φ_j results in a System Abort failure (i.e. non-mission capable status) $\dot{\Phi}_j = 1$ and as such that $\Phi_j \subset \dot{\Phi}$.

4 APPLICATIONS

When the functional severity is defined a-priori the metrics of MTBSA and MTBEFF are fully defined and may be further decomposed (accurately and completely) to the components of the system or SoS; enabling an informed allocation of reliability to the constituent parts of the system.

Further and more importantly, this knowledge can be used to influence and support a Design for Reliability (DFR) approach. First, those functions that are critical may be supported by heterogeneous or homogeneous redundancy. That is, homogeneous redundancy is the use of more than one identical component that individually is capable of supporting a function or functional sub-set. Heterogeneous redundancy is at the functional level using two dissimilar components to support a given function. An example might be the use of a manual crank to raise a mast in addition to a motor to do the same.

Second, those components that result in single point failures (SPF) of System Abort severity, denoted by $\dot{\mathbf{X}}$, can be identified and prioritized for assignment of resources. Specifically, further and more rigorous analyses (e.g. Physics of Failure Analysis) may be applied to these critical parts. Similarly, more focused testing may be applied to this same subset of components to ensure to most critical items in the design receive the appropriate level of focus and investment. This is the logical components on which to invest in Highly Accelerated Life Testing (HALT) and Highly Accelerated

Stress Testing (HAST).

We consider a sample platform – highly simplified for ease of illustration. This is a stationary firing platform with range, accuracy, tracking, and optical functional requirements. Further, the system is decomposed to a physical component set including: weapon, fire control sub-system, laser range finder (LRF), day optical site, and IR Camera.

The requirement set is given by:

Table I. Requirement Set

ID	Requirement
1	The SYSTEM shall be capable of direct fire at ranges of at least 2 kilometers
2	The SYSTEM shall be capable of automatically tracking targets at 8 kilometers
3	The SYSTEM shall provide target accuracy of 2 meters CEP
4	The SYSTEM shall provide day AND night optics

These requirements are denoted as Φ_j for $j=1,2,..4$. The design results in the following components, denoted as below:

- Weapon, X_1
- Optical Site, X_2
- Fire Control, X_3
- Laser Range Finder, X_4
- IR Camera, X_5

Next, these are mapped via the graph \mathbf{G} .

Table II. Functional to Physics Trace

	X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4	X_5
Φ_1	1	1	1	1	0
Φ_2	0	1	0	0	1
Φ_3	1	1	1	1	0
Φ_4	0	1	0	0	1

However, this is not defined for multi-state. Adopting the approach proposed herein the requirements would have been defined with the failure severity attribute included.

Table III. Functional Failure Severity

	Failure Severity	$\phi \subset \dot{\Phi}$
Φ_1	SA	1
Φ_2	EFF	0
Φ_3	SA	1
Φ_4	EFF	0

This classification allows us to reduce \mathbf{G} to its sub-graph that includes only the critical (SA) failure severity functions. *Sub-graph* being a graph that contains common vertices and

edges as the graph to which it is subsidiary.

Table IV. System Abort Sub-graph

	X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4	X_5
Φ_1	1	1	1	1	0
Φ_3	1	1	1	1	0

It is quickly apparent that component 5, the IR Camera is not critical to the system because it does not support a critical function. Now, the value of this fairly straight forward approach can be realized. First, we may allocate our reliability requirements for MTBSA and MTBEFF appropriately, that is components such as the IR Camera will not receive an MTBSA allocation; where as the others will.

In addition, we can determine that the always limited resources in a reliability improvement or growth program should be focused on the first four components, rather than the 5th.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A paradigm shift is required to truly realize the benefits of upfront design for reliability initiatives. Regardless of program, reliability resources are always finite and constrained. To make the best use of those resources knowledge of component criticality is a necessity early in the requirements definition process as opposed to waiting to do the same just prior to test start.

REFERENCES

1. Ramirez-Marquez, Jose E.; Coit, David W. (2004) A heuristic for solving the redundancy allocation problem for multi-state series-parallel systems. Reliability Engineering & System Safety, Mar 2004, Vol. 83 Issue 3.
2. Ramirez-Marquez, Jose E.; Coit, David W. (2005) A Monte-Carlo simulation approach for approximating multi-state two-terminal reliability. Reliability Engineering & System Safety, Feb 2005, Vol. 87 Issue 2.
3. Ramirez-Marquez, Jose E.; Coit, David W. (2007) Multi-state component criticality analysis for reliability improvement in multi-state systems. Reliability Engineering & System Safety, In Press, Corrected Proof
4. Li, Wenjian; Pham, Hoang. (2005) Reliability Modeling of Multi-State Degraded Systems With Multi-Competing Failures and Random Shocks. IEEE Transactions on Reliability, Jun 2005, Vol. 54 Issue 2
5. Rocco S., Claudio M.; Muselli, Marco.(2005) Approximate multi-state reliability expressions using a new machine learning technique. Reliability Engineering & System Safety, Sep 2005, Vol. 89 Issue 3.
6. Satitsatian, Sarintip; Kapur, Kailash C. (2006) An Algorithm for Lower Reliability Bounds of Multistate Two-Terminal Networks. IEEE Transactions on Reliability, Jun 2006, Vol. 55 Issue 2.

7. Ding, Yi; Wang, Peng; Lisnianski, Anatoly. (2006) Optimal reserve management for restructured power generating systems. Reliability Engineering & System Safety, Jul 2006, Vol. 91 Issue 7.
8. Ramirez-Marquez, Jose E.; Rocco, Claudio M.; Gebre, Bethel A.; Coit, David W.; Tortorella, Michael. (2006) New insights on multi-state component criticality and importance. Reliability Engineering & System Safety, Aug 2006, Vol. 91 Issue 8.
9. Ming J. Zuo; Zhigang Tian; Hong-Zhong Huang. (2007) An efficient method for reliability evaluation of multistate networks given all minimal path vectors. IIE Transactions, Aug 2007, Vol. 39 Issue 8.
10. Ramirez-Marquez, Jose E.; Coit, David W. (2007) Optimization of system reliability in the presence of common cause failures. Reliability Engineering & System Safety, Oct 2007, Vol. 92 Issue 10.
11. Wattanapongskorn, Naruemon; Coit, David W. (2007) Fault-tolerant embedded system design and optimization considering reliability estimation uncertainty. Reliability Engineering & System Safety, Apr 2007, Vol. 92 Issue 4.
12. Agarwal, Manju; Gupta, Rashika. (2007) Homogeneous redundancy optimization in multi-state series-parallel systems: A heuristic approach. IIE

Transactions, Mar2007, Vol. 39 Issue 3.

13. Way Kuo. (2007) Recent Advances in Optimal Reliability Allocation. IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man & Cybernetics: Part A, Mar 2007, Vol. 37 Issue 2.

BIOGRAPHIES

Jason L. Cook, CRE
Quality Engineering & System Assurance Directorate
US Army - Armament Research Development Engineering
Center (ARDEC)
Bldg 62 North – Picatinny Arsenal, NJ, USA 07806-5000
Work (973) 724-3920; Jason.Cook1@us.army.mil

Jason Cook is the Chief of the Reliability Management Branch for the Quality Engineering and System Assurance Directorate at Picatinny Arsenal. He holds a Bachelors Degree and Masters Degree in Mechanical Engineering. Jason is a Ph.D. Candidate at Stevens Institute of Technology. In addition, he holds a certification from the ASQ as a Reliability Engineer. Jason is also a member of the ASQ Reliability Division. Research interest in network and SoS reliability are due to his experience on the Army's Future Combat System program.